

1 **Spatiotemporal representations of contextual associations for real-world objects**

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16 **Abstract**

17 In the real world, objects always appear in context. Many objects are reliably associated
18 with a certain scene context (e.g., pots appear in kitchens) and other objects that appear
19 in the same context (e.g., pans appear together with pots). Previous neuroimaging work
20 suggests that such contextual associations shape the neural representation of isolated
21 objects even in the absence of the scene context. Yet, three key questions remain
22 unanswered: (1) How do representations of contextual associations relate to perceptual
23 and categorical representation in visual cortex, (2) how do they emerge across time, and
24 (3) how are they mechanistically implemented? To answer these questions, we recorded
25 fMRI and EEG while participants (human, both sexes) viewed isolated objects
26 stemming from two scene contexts. Multivariate pattern analysis on the neural data
27 revealed that objects from the same context were coded more similarly than objects
28 from different contexts in object-selective LOC and scene-selective PPA, even when
29 systematically controlling for perceptual and categorical similarities. Such contextual
30 relation representations emerged relatively late during visual processing (i.e., after

61 objects with stronger contextual associations (i.e., cooking pots implying a kitchen
62 context) elicited greater activation in the scene-selective parahippocampal place area
63 (PPA) and object-selective area lateral occipital cortex (LOC) than objects without such
64 associations (i.e., bins found across a range of scene contexts). More recently, Bonner
65 and Epstein (2021) demonstrated that the PPA represents object co-occurrence statistics,
66 such that objects sharing contextual associations (e.g., an oven and a dishwasher,
67 typically found together in a kitchen) elicit more similar neural responses than those
68 not sharing such associations (e.g., an oven and an armchair, typically found in different
69 scene contexts). This finding suggests that object representations in scene-selective
70 cortex are organized by contextual associations—likely providing a representational
71 link between scene and object processing. However, three key questions about
72 representations of contextual associations remain unanswered. These pertain to (1) the
73 relation of contextual representations to perceptual and categorical representations, (2)
74 the temporal emergence of contextual representations, and (3) the neural mechanisms
75 that give rise to contextual representations.

76 First, the exact relationship between contextual relation representations and other
77 representational organizations in visual cortex, such as perceptual and categorical
78 representations, remains unclear. Disentangling these representations is critical,
79 because objects that frequently co-occur in the same context often share perceptual and
80 categorical similarity. For example, most cooking utensils are metallic and shiny tools,
81 conflating perceptual, categorical, and contextual similarities. Without
82 comprehensively controlling the potentially confounding attributes, it remains unclear
83 whether representational similarities truly reflect the objects' associated context.

84 Second, it is unclear how contextual relation representations emerge across time.
85 They could emerge relatively late during visual processing, after the computation of
86 perceptual and categorical object features. Such late contextual representations might
87 be driven by more abstract and memory-related processes (Bar & Aminoff, 2003, Bar
88 et al., 2008; Aminoff et al., 2013) that are coded in anterior subregions of the PPA
89 (Baldassano et al., 2013, 2016). Alternatively, contextual association may emerge
90 concurrently with categorical representations, suggesting parallel computations of
91 object category and context in object- and scene-selective cortex.

92 Third, different mechanisms could mediate the representation of contextual

93 associations. The representations could emerge from a direct co-activation of object
94 representations, akin to a spread of activation across objects from the same context
95 (Bonner & Epstein, 2021; Nah & Geng, 2022), or form shared activation of scene-
96 category representations, consistent with PPA's role in scene categorization (Epstein &
97 Kanwisher, 1998; Walther et al., 2009). Notably, these two mechanisms are
98 complementary and could both contribute at different processing stages.

99 We addressed these three open issues by showing participants individual object
100 images from a stimulus set that orthogonally manipulated contextual and categorical
101 relationships while tightly controlling for perceptual similarity. Using multivariate
102 pattern analysis (MVPA) on fMRI and EEG data, we mapped neural representations of
103 contextual associations across space and time. Our results provide three key insights:
104 First, contextual associations are encoded in object- and scene-selective areas, when
105 systematically controlling for perceptual and categorical similarities. Second, such
106 contextual relation representations emerge relatively late in visual processing, after
107 perceptual and categorical object processing, and more strongly in anterior PPA. Third,
108 while initial representations of contextual associations are likely mediated by a co-
109 activation of contextually related objects, later representations may also reflect a co-
110 activation of associated scene category representations.

111 **Materials And Methods**

112 **Participants**

113 Thirty-four healthy volunteers (22 females, 11 males, and one preferred not to reveal,
114 age = 25.21 ± 4.44 years) participated in the EEG experiment, and another 33 (19
115 females, age = 24.14 ± 3.34 years) participated in the fMRI experiment. Sample sizes
116 were chosen to obtain ~80% power for detecting a hypothetical medium effect of $d =$
117 0.5 at $p < 0.05$ (two-sided t-test). All participants were native German speakers and had
118 normal or corrected-to-normal vision. They provided written informed consent prior to
119 participation and were compensated at a rate of 10 euros per hour. The study was
120 approved by the Ethics Committee of Justus Liebig University Giessen and conducted
121 in accordance with the 6th revision of the Declaration of Helsinki. One fMRI participant
122 did not complete all experimental runs and was therefore excluded from the analyses.

123 **Stimuli**

Object representations of contextual associations

124 A total of 24 real-world objects were selected, stemming from two contexts (12 kitchen
125 objects and 12 garden objects) and two categories (12 tools and 12 non-tools). These
126 objects were grouped into six sets of four items each, each of which contained one
127 object per condition (i.e., 1 kitchen tool, 1 garden tool, 1 kitchen non-tool, and 1 garden
128 non-tool). Within each set, objects were matched for their overall shape (see Fig. 1A).
129 There were four exemplars per object, yielding a total of 96 unique stimuli. All stimuli
130 were positioned against a white square background ($5^\circ \times 5^\circ$ visual angle). The resulting
131 images were gray-scaled and matched for overall luminance using MATLAB's Image
132 Processing Toolbox.

133 We further assessed whether there were any visual differences between objects
134 from the same and different contextual or categorical conditions using a VGG16 deep
135 neural network (pre-trained on object categorization) and a hierarchical model of early
136 visual processing (HMAX; Riesenhuber & Poggio, 1999). For this, we first computed
137 Pearson correlations between layer-wise activation patterns for each pair of stimuli.
138 This yielded a 24-by-24 representational similarity matrix (RSM) at every layer of
139 DNN and the C1 layer in HMAX, which approximates feature processing in V1. Next,
140 we created two predictor RSMs to model the image similarity matrix: (1) A contextual
141 RSM, indicating whether object pairs belonged to the same context (e.g., both from the
142 kitchen or garden) or different contexts; (2) A categorical RSM, indicating whether
143 objects shared the same category (e.g., both tools or both non-tools) or different
144 categories. We then vectorized all RSMs, retaining only the lower off-diagonal values.
145 Next, the vectorized DNN/HMAX RSM was predicted by a linear combination of the
146 vectorized contextual and categorical RSMs in a regression model for each layer.
147 Significant predictions were established from permutation tests, in which the rows and
148 columns of the DNN/HMAX RSM (1,000 iterations) were repeatedly shuffled to
149 generate null distributions of beta estimates. The resulting p-values were corrected for
150 comparisons across layers using false discovery rate (FDR) corrections. Within-
151 condition (objects from the same context/category) correlations did not differ
152 significantly from between-condition (objects from the different contexts/categories)
153 correlations (DNN: largest contextual effect: $\beta = -0.03$, corrected $p = .90$, layer 4;
154 largest categorical effect: $\beta = 0.11$, corrected $p = .34$, layer 15; C1-HMAX: contextual
155 effect: $\beta = -0.048$, corrected $p = .81$, categorical effect: $\beta = -0.053$, corrected $p = .81$)
156 effects, indicating no differential contribution of image features to the manipulated

157 factors.

158 Furthermore, we used 24 scene images to test for shared representations between
159 object images and their associated scene context. These images included 12 kitchen
160 scenes and 12 garden scenes. None of our object stimuli were featured in these scenes.
161 The selected images were gray-scaled and matched for overall luminance using
162 MATLAB's Image Processing Toolbox. We then used a DNN to evaluate whether the
163 objects shared a greater image similarity with the associated scene (e.g., rolling pin -
164 kitchen) than the non-associated scene (e.g., rolling pin - garden). For this, we first
165 computed Pearson correlations between layer-wise activation patterns in a VGG16
166 DNN and the C1 layer in a HMAX, correlating activations for each object with
167 activations for the two scenes (associated and non-associated). Next, we calculated the
168 difference between the associated and non-associated conditions and tested the
169 difference against zero using permutation t-tests with FDR correction (see above).
170 Objects were equally correlated with the associated scene and the non-associated scenes
171 (DNN: largest difference = .0089, corrected $p = .769$, layer 16; HMAX-C1: difference
172 = -0.0006, corrected $p = .53$), suggesting the objects did not systematically share image
173 features with their associated scenes.

174 **Paradigm**

175 In both EEG and fMRI experiments, participants first completed a questionnaire to
176 assess their knowledge about the 24 selected objects. Here, the (German) words
177 representing all objects were presented, and participants were asked whether they knew
178 the object. If a participant did not know an object, the experimenter described it to
179 ensure accurate identification during the task. During the main experiment, the
180 participants first performed an object one-back task, indicating whether an occasionally
181 presented word probe matched the previously shown object. Then, they performed the
182 scene one-back task following the same logic (Fig. 1B). Finally, participants completed
183 a co-occurrence questionnaire that covered all object pairs, designed to validate our
184 assignment of objects to the two contexts. The questionnaire consisted of two parts: (1)
185 object–scene co-occurrence and (2) object–object co-occurrence. In the first part,
186 participants indicated where they typically encounter each object—either in a kitchen
187 or a garden. In the second part, participants rated on a scale from 0 to 100 how
188 frequently the two objects co-occur in daily life, and how similar their functions are—

Object representations of contextual associations

189 that is, whether the objects are used in a similar way and for a similar purpose. Across
190 both experiments, all selected objects were rated as more frequently encountered within
191 their assigned context, and co-occurrence between objects was consistently lower in the
192 between-context condition compared to the within-context condition.

193 In the fMRI experiment, participants first completed an object practice block with
194 30 trials (24 images and 6 one-back trials) outside the scanner. Following an anatomical
195 scan, we first ran an 8-minute functional localizer task comprising four conditions:
196 fixation, object, scene, and scrambled objects. Each condition included 8 blocks, with
197 16 stimuli presented in each block. Stimuli were shown for 0.5 seconds each, followed
198 by a 0.5-second interstimulus interval. The order of blocks was counterbalanced, and
199 the same condition was never presented in consecutive blocks. After that, participants
200 completed 10 object blocks and 2 scene blocks, each with 120 trials (96 images and 24
201 word-probes). Each object block began with a 6-second fixation dot and contained 96
202 images (featuring all object exemplars) with pseudo-randomization to prevent
203 repetition of the same object (e.g., two rolling pin images shown consecutively) and 24
204 word-probe trials inserted at random positions in this sequence. In each scene block,
205 we first pseudo-randomized 24 trials (featuring all scene exemplars) and subsequently
206 inserted 6 word-probes (half kitchen and half garden); the procedure was applied four
207 times, yielding 96 images and 24 probe trials for each block. For both types of blocks,
208 each trial started with a 1.7-second fixation, followed by either a 0.3-second image or
209 a 2.3-second word-probe display. The total fMRI session, including anatomical and
210 localizer scans, lasted approximately 90 minutes, and the follow-up co-occurrence
211 questionnaire again lasted around 30 minutes.

212 In the EEG experiment, participants sat in an illuminated room at a distance of 57
213 cm from the monitor. Participants first completed a practice object block with 30 trials.
214 The following experiment consisted of 8 blocks of 240 trials. In each object block, 96
215 image trials were pseudo-randomized to prevent repetition of the same object, and 24
216 word-probes were inserted at random positions in this sequence. This procedure was
217 applied two times, resulting in 192 image trials and 48 probe trials per block. After that,
218 participants performed a scene practice block containing 12 scenes (half kitchen and
219 half garden) and 4 one-back trials, followed by two experimental blocks of 240 trials
220 each. In each scene block, we first pseudo-randomized 24 trials (featuring all scene

221 exemplars) and subsequently inserted 6 word-probes (half kitchen and half garden); the
222 procedure was applied eight times, yielding 192 images and 48 probe trials for each
223 block. For both block types, each trial started with a fixation cross, which varied
224 randomly between 0.8, 1, and 1.2 seconds, followed by a 0.3-second stimulus display.
225 For the one-back trials, the word probes remained on screen until a response was made.
226 Participants were instructed to maintain central fixation throughout, respond as quickly
227 and accurately as possible in the one-back trials, and blink during ISIs. Participants
228 could pause between blocks, and they could self-initiate the next block. The full EEG
229 session lasted approximately 90 minutes, and the follow-up co-occurrence
230 questionnaire lasted around 30 minutes.

231 **fMRI recording and preprocessing**

232 MRI data was acquired using a 3T Siemens Magnetom PRISMA Scanner equipped with
233 a 64-channel head coil. Functional images were obtained using T2*-weighted gradient-
234 echo echo-planar imaging (EPI) with the following parameters: repetition time (TR) =
235 1850 ms, echo time (TE) = 30 ms, flip angle = 75°, in-plane voxel size = 2.2 mm x 2.2
236 mm x 2.2 mm, 58 slices with a 20% inter-slice gap (distance factor), field of view =
237 220 mm, matrix size = 100 × 100, and descending slice acquisition. Additionally, a
238 high-resolution anatomical reference was collected using a T1-weighted MP-RAGE
239 sequence with a voxel size of 1 mm³.

240 MRI data preprocessing was conducted using MATLAB and SPM12
241 (www.fil.ion.ucl.ac.uk/spm/). Functional images were first corrected for geometric
242 distortions using the SPM FieldMap toolbox (Hutton et al., 2002) and subsequently
243 realigned to account for head motion. Each participant's structural T1-weighted image
244 was coregistered to the mean of the realigned functional images. Normalization
245 parameters for transformation to Montreal Neurological Institute (MNI) standard
246 space—and their inverse—were then estimated.

247 For each run, functional data were modeled using a general linear model (GLM)
248 that included separate regressors for the 24 objects. Additionally, six motion parameters
249 obtained during realignment were included as nuisance regressors, resulting in a total
250 of 30 regressors per run.

251 **fMRI regions of interest definition**

252 fMRI analyses were focused on three regions of interest (ROIs): scene-selective
253 parahippocampal place area (PPA), object-selective lateral occipital cortex (LOC), and
254 early visual cortex (EVC). ROI masks were defined using individual localizer data
255 constrained by group-level activation masks from functional brain atlases: For the PPA
256 and LOC, we first combined left and right hemispheres and identified the top 500 voxels
257 showing the highest t-values from the contrasts [scene > object + scrambled] and
258 [object > scrambled], respectively, within regional masks derived from the atlas by
259 Julian et al. (2012). For the EVC, all voxels from V1, V2, and V3 (including both dorsal
260 and ventral subdivisions) were selected based on probabilistic maps from the Wang et
261 al. (2015) atlas.

262 For analyses specifically targeting posterior and anterior PPA subregions, the PPA
263 was further divided at MNI coordinate $y = -42$ following Baldassano et al. (2016).
264 Within each subregion, the top 250 voxels were selected based on the scene > object +
265 scrambled contrast from the localizer.

266 **fMRI RSA analysis**

267 We used representational similarity analysis (RSA) to relate the contextual, categorical,
268 and perceptual similarity of objects to their neural similarity (Fig. 1D). We first checked
269 task performance to make sure participants followed the instructions. Task accuracy
270 was $93.50\% \pm 1.12\%$ for object blocks and $93.23\% \pm 1.84\%$ for scene blocks,
271 indicating that participants followed the instructions and paid attention to the objects
272 and scenes. We averaged the fMRI beta maps from the first-level GLM analysis for
273 each object across all exemplars and repeated trials across runs. Next, we computed the
274 Pearson correlation of multi-voxel response patterns (i.e., patterns of beta values across
275 voxels) between all pairs of objects in each ROI, resulting in a 24-by-24 RSM for each
276 ROI. Next, we created three predictor RSMs to model the neural data: (1) A contextual
277 RSM, indicating whether object pairs belonged to the same context (e.g., both from the
278 kitchen or garden) or different contexts; (2) A categorical RSM, indicating whether
279 objects shared the same category (e.g., both tools or both non-tools) or different
280 categories; (3) a perceptual RSM, constructed from the reaction time of the same-
281 different task (Fig. 1C). For this, an additional independent group of participants ($N =$
282 34) was recruited, indicating whether two simultaneously presented object images were
283 the same or different. The RTs on the different-object condition were used as a measure

284 of perceptual similarity, where longer RTs indicate higher perceptual similarity between
285 the two objects (Jacob & Arun, 2020; Yeh & Peelen, 2022). The RSM was based on the
286 average of the 34 participants. To examine whether RTs from the same–different task
287 reflect categorical or contextual information, we tested Pearson correlations among the
288 three predictor RSMs. No significant correlations were observed (perceptual RSM vs.
289 categorical RSM: $r = 0.096$, $p = 0.11$; perceptual RSM vs. contextual RSM: $r = -0.064$,
290 $p = 0.29$; categorical RSM vs. contextual RSM: $r = -0.046$, $p = 0.45$). We then
291 vectorized all RSMs, retaining only the lower off-diagonal values, excluding the
292 diagonal. Next, the vectorized neural RSMs were predicted by a linear combination of
293 the vectorized contextual, categorical, and perceptual RSMs in a linear regression
294 model (Fig. 1D). Finally, we tested whether the resulting beta estimates were larger than
295 zero using one-sample t-tests, one-tailed. FDR correction was applied to control the
296 multiple comparisons across the 9 tests (3 predictors and 3 ROIs).

297 To investigate the association between object and scene representations, we first
298 averaged the fMRI beta values for each object and scene across all exemplars. Next, we
299 correlated multi-voxel response patterns for each object with multi-voxel response
300 patterns for the two scene categories using Pearson correlations. For each object, this
301 resulted in one within-context (e.g., rolling pin and kitchen) and one between-context
302 (e.g., rolling pin and garden) correlation. Next, we computed the difference between
303 the within-context correlations and between-context correlations for each object and
304 then averaged across objects. The resulting differences were tested against zero using
305 one-sided t-tests at the group level.

306 **EEG recording and preprocessing**

307 Electrophysiological signals were recorded using a 64-channel Easycap system with a
308 Brain Products amplifier, sampled at 1,000 Hz. The setup included 56 electrodes
309 distributed across both hemispheres (including FP1/FP2, AF3/AF4, AF7/AF8, F1/F2,
310 F3/F4, F5/F6, F7/F8, FC1/FC2, FC3/FC4, FT5/FT6, FT7/FT8, FT9/FT10, C1/C2,
311 C3/C4, C5/C6, T7/T8, CP1/CP2, CP3/CP4, CP5/CP6, TP7/TP8, P1/P2, P3/P4, P5/P6,
312 P7/P8, PO3/PO4, PO7/PO8, PO9/PO10, and O1/O2) and seven electrodes along the
313 midline (Fz, FCz, Cz, CPz, Pz, POz, and Oz). The ground electrode was placed at AFz,
314 while Fz was used as the online reference. Electrodes FP1/FP2 and FT9/FT10 were
315 repurposed for monitoring vertical and horizontal eye movements and were excluded

316 from EEG analysis. Electrode impedances were maintained below 20 k Ω . Event
317 triggers were transmitted from the stimulus presentation computer to the EEG
318 acquisition system via a parallel port.

319 EEG data were preprocessed offline using the Fieldtrip toolbox (Oostenveld et al.,
320 2011) in MATLAB (MathWorks). The TP10 channel, which exhibited excessive noise
321 in most participants, was excluded and subsequently interpolated using the average
322 signal from its neighboring electrodes. Ocular artifacts, including those from blinks and
323 eye movements, were identified and removed through independent component analysis
324 (ICA) combined with visual inspection of the components for each participant. The
325 EEG data were then re-referenced to the average of all electrodes, excluding those
326 related to ocular activity (FP1, FP2, FT9, and FT10), and segmented into epochs
327 ranging from -100 ms to 500 ms relative to stimulus onset. Baseline correction was
328 applied using the pre-stimulus interval (-100 to 0 ms). The data was then downsampled
329 to 250 Hz for the following analysis. Given our focus on object representations in the
330 visual system, the anterior electrodes were excluded in the following analyses (Kaiser
331 et al., 2019; Yeh et al., 2025; Robinson et al., 2025). All further analyses are based on
332 the remaining 37 electrodes (Cz, CPz, Pz, POz, Oz, C1/C2, C3/C4, C5/C6, CP1/CP2,
333 CP3/CP4, CP5/CP6, T7/T8, TP7/TP8, P1/P2, P3/P4, P5/P6, P7/P8, PO3/PO4,
334 PO7/PO8, PO9/PO10, and O1/O2).

335 EEG RSA analysis

336 To investigate how contextual, categorical, and perceptual factors influence the time
337 course of object representations, we again used RSA, similar to the fMRI analysis (Fig.
338 1D). We first checked the task performance to make sure participants followed the
339 instructions. Task accuracy was $89.92\% \pm 1.05\%$ for object blocks and $93.57\% \pm 0.92\%$
340 % for scene blocks, indicating that participants followed the instructions and paid
341 attention to the objects and scenes. For each time point in the EEG epochs, we first
342 averaged the EEG signals for each object across all exemplars and trials. Next, we
343 computed the Pearson correlation of EEG signals between all pairs of objects at each
344 time point. This yielded a 24-by-24 neural representational similarity matrix (RSM) at
345 every time point (250 Hz resolution). Next, we created three predictor RSMs to model
346 the neural data: (1) A contextual RSM, indicating whether object pairs belonged to the
347 same context (e.g., both from the kitchen or garden) or different contexts, (2) a

348 categorical RSM, indicating whether objects shared the same category (e.g., both tools
349 or both non-tools) or different categories, and (3) A perceptual RSM, constructed from
350 the reaction time of the same-different task. (in the same way as for the fMRI analysis).
351 We then vectorized all RSMs, retaining only the lower off-diagonal values. Next,
352 vectorized neural RSMs were predicted by a linear combination of the vectorized
353 contextual, categorical, and perceptual RSMs in a linear regression model. Finally, we
354 tested whether the resulting beta estimates were greater than zero (one-sided) at each
355 4-ms timepoint within the 0–500 ms window following stimulus onset, using cluster-
356 based non-parametric permutation t-tests (Maris & Oostenveld, 2007). Specifically, t-
357 tests were first performed at each time point. Time points exceeding a predefined
358 threshold ($p < .05$) and occurring consecutively were grouped into clusters. For each
359 cluster, the sum of the t-values was computed and compared against a null distribution
360 generated from 1,000 Monte Carlo random permutations. Statistical significance was
361 determined using a cluster-level correction for multiple comparisons (one-tailed, p
362 $< .05$).

363 To investigate the association between object and scene representations, we first
364 computed event-related potentials (ERPs) for each object and scene across all
365 exemplars. Next, we correlated ERP patterns (across electrodes) for each object with
366 ERP patterns for the two scene contexts using Pearson correlations, separately for each
367 4-ms time point. For each object and time point, this resulted in one within-context (e.g.,
368 rolling pin and kitchen) and one between-context (e.g., rolling pin and garden)
369 correlation. Next, we computed the difference between the within-context correlations
370 and between-context correlations for each object and then averaged across objects. The
371 resulting differences were tested against zero using one-sided t-tests at the group level
372 with non-parametric cluster correction (see above).

373

374 **Results**

375 Here, we applied RSA to fMRI and EEG data to investigate where and when contextual
376 associations shape object representations, while controlling for perceptual and
377 categorical similarity. We first focus on the fMRI results, revealing which brain regions
378 represent contextual object relations.

379 Contextual object relations are represented in object- and scene-selective cortex

380 By performing RSA on the fMRI data, we aimed to investigate which visual cortex
381 regions reflect contextual relations, focusing on PPA, LOC, and EVC (Fig. 2A). We
382 observed contextual effects in PPA [$t(31) = 2.14$, FDR-corrected $p = .036$] and LOC
383 [$t(31) = 2.38$, FDR-corrected $p = .027$], suggesting a representation of contextual object
384 information in both object- and scene-selective cortex. No contextual effects were
385 observed in EVC [$t(31) = 0.23$, FDR-corrected $p = .460$]. Categorical effects were only
386 observed in LOC [$t(31) = 6.07$, FDR-corrected $p < .001$] but not in PPA [$t(31) = 1.00$,
387 FDR-corrected $p = .243$] and EVC [$t(31) = -1.21$, FDR-corrected $p = .883$]. Finally,
388 perceptual effects were observed in LOC [$t(31) = 5.58$, FDR-corrected $p < .001$] and
389 EVC [$t(31) = 3.85$, FDR-corrected $p < .001$], but not in PPA [$t(31) = -1.73$, FDR-
390 corrected $p = .953$]. Together, these results reveal an emergence of both contextual and
391 categorical effects in object processing regions, contrasting with only contextual
392 information represented in scene-selective PPA.

393 Next, we examined how contextual effects emerge across PPA subregions. Prior
394 studies have shown that the posterior PPA is more responsive to visually driven
395 information, whereas the anterior PPA is associated with conceptual processing
396 (Baldassano et al., 2013, 2016). Following Baldassano et al. (2016), we divided the PPA
397 at MNI coordinate $y = -42$ and applied the identical RSA to each subregion (see
398 Methods fMRI RSA). Interestingly, we found a significant contextual effect only in the
399 anterior PPA [$t(31) = 1.95$, $p = .030$], but not in the posterior PPA [$t(31) = 0.96$, $p = .173$],
400 and the contextual effect was larger in anterior PPA than in posterior PPA [$t(31) = 2.01$,
401 $p = .052$, two-tailed] (Fig. 2B).

402 These results indicate that contextual relations are represented in object-selective
403 LOC and scene-selective PPA, but not in EVC. Together with previous fMRI studies
404 (Bar & Aminoff, 2003; Bonner & Epstein, 2021), this pattern suggests that
405 representations of contextual object relations arise from relatively late interactions
406 among representations across high-level visual cortex. To characterize the precise
407 timing of contextual relation representations, we next performed RSA on the EEG data.

**408 Contextual object relations are represented during the late stages of perceptual
409 processing**

410 We investigated the time course of contextual object representations using RSA on the
411 EEG data. Contextual effects emerged in two temporal clusters. First, from 364 ms to
412 411 ms after stimulus onset (cluster $p=.008$), and second, from 464 ms after stimulus
413 onset to the end of the epoch (cluster $p=.040$; Fig. 2C). Critically, these contextual
414 effects emerged later than perceptual effects, which were evident from 84 ms after
415 stimulus onset (cluster $p <.001$), and later than categorical effects, which were evident
416 from 208 ms (cluster $p =.044$) and from 312 ms (cluster $p <.001$) after stimulus onset.
417 These temporal dynamics reveal that, upon viewing an object, there is a sequential
418 emergence of information, with perceptual information followed by categorical
419 information (here: whether the object is a tool or not), and finally contextual
420 information (here: whether an object is found in the kitchen or garden).

421 **Representations of contextual object relations may partly reflect the activation of** 422 **scene representations**

423 Next, we examined whether the isolated objects and scenes evoke shared
424 representations, which would indicate that contextual representations are mediated by
425 an automatic co-activation of associated scene representations. Using RSA on the fMRI
426 and EEG data, we identified the spatiotemporal signatures of this putative co-activation.
427 Specifically, we compared response patterns between objects and their associated
428 scenes (within-context correlation) versus the non-associated scenes (between-context
429 correlation) (Fig. 3A).

430 For the fMRI analysis, we focused on the posterior and anterior PPA subdivisions,
431 given that representations of scene categories should form in the PPA (Walther et al.,
432 2009) and given that the previous contextual relation effects emerged in the anterior
433 portion of the PPA. However, we did not observe significant effects, neither in the
434 anterior PPA [$t(31) = 0.51$, corrected $p = .308$] nor in the posterior PPA [$t(31) = 0.42$, p
435 $= .338$] (Fig. 3B). Further, no effects emerged in regions outside of the PPA (EVC, LOC,
436 all $t(31) < 1.31$, $p >.1$).

437 Performing this analysis on the EEG data, we found significantly higher within-
438 context than between-context correlations from 452 ms after stimulus onset (cluster p
439 $= .011$; Fig. 3C). This suggests that late representations of contextual object relations
440 (i.e., the second cluster found in the previous analysis; Fig. 2C) are partly related to the
441 co-activation of associated scene representations.

442 In sum, our EEG results suggest that late representations of contextual object
443 relations (emerging around 460 ms after stimulus onset) may partly relate to the co-
444 activation of associated scenes. However, we were not able to localize such
445 representations in our fMRI analysis. Further studies are needed to fully clarify whether
446 and how the co-activation of scene representations contributes to contextual codes in
447 object vision.

448 **Discussion**

449 In this study, we used fMRI and EEG to investigate where and when contextual
450 associations shape neural representations of real-world objects. Applying RSA on fMRI
451 and EEG signals, we found that contextual information is represented in object-
452 selective areas LOC and scene-selective anterior PPA. Such representations emerged
453 during late stages of visual object processing, from around 360 ms after stimulus onset.
454 Contextual representations first reflected similarities among objects from the same
455 scene context, and subsequently showed signs of the co-activation of object
456 representations and their associated scene category representations or shared
457 conceptual representations with the associated scene category.

458 The finding that contextual relations are encoded in scene-selective PPA, is
459 consistent with the fMRI results of Bonner and Epstein (2021). By using a tightly
460 controlled stimulus set and systematically accounting for categorical and perceptual
461 similarity in our analysis, our results demonstrate a genuine representation of contextual
462 associations in PPA, rather than shared perceptual or categorical features. We also found
463 contextual object representations in LOC, consistent with Bar and Aminoff's (2003)
464 report of objects with stronger contextual associations also activating LOC more
465 strongly. The contextual effects in LOC may reflect the co-activation of object concepts
466 through learned object-to-object relations encountered in real-world environments
467 (Kim & Biederman, 2011; Kaiser et al., 2019; Vo, 2021).

468 Within the PPA, we found that contextual relations were encoded in the anterior
469 but not the posterior PPA. While the posterior PPA is more strongly connected to
470 occipital areas, supporting the processing of visual features such as spatial layout
471 (Baldassano et al., 2013, 2016; Nasr et al., 2014; Lescroart & Gallant, 2019), the
472 anterior PPA is more strongly connected to the hippocampus, particularly its anterior
473 part, which is involved in episodic memory encoding and retrieval, environmental

474 representation, and scene construction for recall and imagination (Baldassano et al.,
475 2016; Zeidman & Maguire, 2016). The emergence of contextual representations in
476 anterior PPA suggests that the brain retrieves relations among co-occurring objects from
477 episodic memory, likely to mentally construct associated scenes and episodes, which
478 may in turn facilitate the recognition of isolated objects (Bar & Aminoff, 2003; Bar,
479 2004; Hayes et al., 2007; Bar et al., 2008; Aminoff et al., 2013; Steel et al., 2023). On
480 this view, contextual representations in PPA may reflect more abstract relational
481 processing rather than the reactivation of concrete visual features such as spatial scene
482 layouts (Epstein, 2008; Mullally & Maguire, 2011, 2013).

483 Our EEG results revealed a sequential emergence of three effects: perceptual
484 effects appeared first (from 84 ms post-stimulus), followed by categorical effects (from
485 208 ms), and finally contextual effects, which emerged later in processing (from 364
486 ms post-stimulus). We observed two distinct temporal clusters during which contextual
487 information was represented: between 364 ~ 411 ms and between 464 ms to the end of
488 the epoch. The sequence of emergence aligns with the hierarchical organization of the
489 visual system, in which early visual cortices process low-level features, while higher-
490 order regions encode more semantic information (Peelen & Caramazza, 2012; Peelen
491 et al., 2013; Clarke et al., 2013; Cichy et al., 2014; Proklova et al., 2016, 2019; Thorat
492 et al., 2019). During this semantic coding stage, contextual effects emerged later than
493 categorical effects, suggesting that contextual processing requires prior computation of
494 object categories, rather than reflecting a form of rapid visual priming among co-
495 occurring objects. The delayed contextual effect is also consistent with MEG findings
496 showing that high-level scene representations (Cichy et al., 2017) and scene-based
497 contextual facilitation of object recognition (Brandman & Peelen, 2017) arise relatively
498 late in visual processing. This indicates that inferring scene context requires additional
499 processing time, perhaps necessitated by memory retrieval from higher-order cortical
500 regions. Here, further studies are needed to clarify the role of memory processes in the
501 formation of contextual relation representations.

502 It is worth noting that two recent EEG studies produced seemingly inconsistent
503 results with ours. First, Kim et al. (2025) did not observe more similar neural
504 representations between objects that are contextually related, here measured by the
505 frequency of object co-occurrence. However, not all stimuli in their study were strongly

506 tied to a specific scene context (e.g., toys, clothing, or body parts can appear in many
507 contexts), and associations to a common scene context may be needed to produce
508 reliable effects. Second, Kallmayer et al. (2024) reported shared representations for
509 objects from the same scene context (e.g., toothbrush and sink) during a much earlier
510 time window (128 – 164 ms post-stimulus) than we did. It is possible that these earlier
511 effects are driven by categorical factors, as categorical similarity was not accounted for
512 in that study.

513 Additionally, in the current study, we defined the category at the superordinate
514 level (i.e., “tool”). While superordinate distinctions are commonly used in object-
515 representation research and are readily discriminable in the visual system (Cichy et al.,
516 2014; Bracci et al., 2017; Grootswagers et al., 2019), everyday categorization more
517 often occurs at the basic level (e.g., “rolling pin” rather than “tool”; Greene & Fei-Fei,
518 2014; Potter & Hagemann, 2014). Consistent with this, neuroimaging studies suggest
519 that basic-level category information can emerge earlier and more robustly than
520 superordinate-level information (Jordan et al., 2015; Bauer & Just, 2017; Greene &
521 Rohan, 2025). Thus, our use of a superordinate-level manipulation may underestimate
522 how early category information can be extracted. Importantly, this does not affect our
523 main conclusion that contextual information emerges later than category information.
524 However, future work could directly test whether the precise timings differ when
525 category is defined at the basic level.

526 The second temporal cluster during which contextual information was represented
527 (from 464 ms to the end of the epoch) overlapped with the time window during which
528 we observed shared representations between objects and their associated scenes (from
529 452 ms to the end of the epoch). This suggests that there might be two distinct stages
530 of contextual representation: An initial co-activation among contextually related objects
531 may be followed by a co-activation of associated object and scene representations or
532 shared conceptual representations with the associated scene category. However, we
533 found no evidence for such a co-activation between objects and scenes in the fMRI, nor
534 in LO and PPA. Previous studies found no shared representations between scenes and
535 individual objects in the PPA either (MacEvoy & Epstein, 2011; Kaiser & Peelen, 2018),
536 but findings in LOC are mixed: Kaiser and Peelen (2018) reporting no shared
537 representations, while MacEvoy and Epstein (2011) could successfully cross-decode

538 between objects and their associated scenes. Here, it is important to note that the
539 MacEvoy and Epstein (2011) study featured the same objects in the individual object
540 and scene conditions, while our study (as well as Kaiser & Peelen, 2018) used scenes
541 that did not contain the individual objects. While the absence of scene-object
542 associations in the fMRI is therefore in line with previous fMRI findings, the difference
543 between our EEG and fMRI experiments is harder to reconcile. One possibility is that
544 EEG signals more faithfully capture activity across distributed regions and thus unveil
545 the underlying interactions between object- and scene-processing regions that drive
546 object-scene associations. At this point, further studies are needed to fully understand
547 whether such co-activations between objects and scenes are reliable and, if so, where
548 they are localized in the brain.

549 Previous behavioral studies demonstrated that context frames facilitate real-world
550 object recognition (Oliva & Torralba, 2007). Such effects manifest as facilitation effects
551 among objects, where target objects are recognized more accurately when presented
552 with context-consistent non-target objects (Auckland et al., 2007), as well as among
553 objects and scenes, where consistent scene context enhances the identification of
554 objects, and vice versa (Davenport & Potter, 2004; Brandman & Peelen, 2017; Leroy
555 et al., 2020; Chen et al., 2022). Our current results suggest that such contextual
556 facilitation is supported by the co-activation of contextually associated object
557 representations and shared scene category representations in visual cortex. These co-
558 activations can sharpen neural representations of ambiguous objects (Brandman &
559 Peelen, 2017; Quek et al., 2025) and scenes (Brandman & Peelen, 2023) and lower the
560 perceptual threshold for upcoming stimuli by pre-activating representations of
561 associated objects and scenes (Tang et al., 2022).

562 **Conclusion**

563 In summary, our findings show that contextual associations of objects are
564 represented in object- and scene-selective regions of the human ventral visual system
565 and emerge during late stages of object processing. Such contextual relation
566 representations emerged for isolated objects, and without a task that encourages their
567 formation, suggesting that objects automatically activate context frames that support
568 visual cognition in real-world environments.

569

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736

737 **Figure 1. Stimuli, task, and schematic of analysis approach.** (A) Stimulus set. 24
 738 objects were used in the experiments. They stemmed from two contexts (kitchen and
 739 garden) and two categories (tool and non-tool). (B) Paradigm for both object (left) and
 740 scene (right) blocks. Participants saw isolated objects or scenes presented in a pseudo-
 741 random sequence and were asked to report whether an occasional word probe (in
 742 German) matched the previous image. (C) Same-different task procedure. Participants
 743 were asked to report whether two simultaneously presented stimuli were the same or
 744 different images. (D) Analysis approach. Neural RSMs constructed from the EEG and
 745 fMRI data were predicted from three model RSMs reflecting the objects' similarities in
 746 (1) contextual relations, (2) categorical relations, and (3) perceptual similarity. For each
 747 predictor, we estimated a beta weight in a linear model, separately for each participant.
 748 These beta weights indicated the contribution of contextual, categorical, and perceptual
 749 factors to temporally and spatially resolved neural activity.

750

751 **Figure 2. RSA results.** (A) fMRI results. Contextual effects were observed in PPA and

Object representations of contextual associations

752 LOC, categorical effects in LOC, and perceptual effects in LOC and EVC. * indicates
753 FDR-corrected $p < 0.05$, one-tailed. (B) fMRI results in PPA subregions. Contextual
754 effects were only found in the anterior PPA. * indicates $p < 0.05$, one-tailed. (C) EEG
755 results. Contextual effects emerged at 364 ms and again at 468 ms after stimulus onset,
756 later than the perceptual effects (from 84 ms) and categorical effects (from 208 ms).
757 Bold lines indicate statistical significance ($p < 0.05$, cluster-level, one-tailed).

758

759 **Figure 3. Results from the scene co-activation RSA.** (A) Schematic of the analysis
760 approach. We first computed correlations between each object and its associated scene
761 (within-context correlation) and the non-associated scene (between-context correlation).
762 Subtracting these two correlations yielded a measure of category-specific object-scene
763 association during object viewing. (B) fMRI results. No significant object-scene
764 associations were observed in the anterior and posterior PPA subregions. (C) EEG
765 results. A significant cluster of scene association emerged around 450 ms after stimulus
766 onset (cluster $p < 0.05$).

767

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